

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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CLINICAL NURSE LEADER PRACTICE AND IMPACT COMPETENCY MODEL:
A DYNAMIC RESPONSE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this doctoral project was to develop meaningful clinical nurse leader (CNL) practice competency forms for a healthcare organization. During the development process of the competency forms, the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) Model was created. The CNL PIC Model was generated following a review of the literature and of healthcare organization's internal sources of communication, as well as the author's experiences as a practicing CNL. This doctoral project led to the development of two manuscripts, one describing the establishment of the CNL practice competency forms and one describing use of the CNL PIC Model to develop CNL practice competency forms.

The manuscripts will be submitted to the *Journal of Professional Nursing (JPN)*. JPN is the official journal of the American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN). The AACN was instrumental in the conception and implementation of the CNL role nationally. It seems appropriate that this peer-reviewed journal be the platform for these manuscripts. Readership of this journal include professional nurses, clinical nurse leaders, educators, administrators, and nurse leaders. Readers will be able to use the CNL PIC Model to create meaningful and valuable CNL practice competency forms for healthcare organizations that employ nurses who are in the CNL role.

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BACKGROUND

The American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN) proposed the Clinical Nurse Leader (CNL) role in 2003 to improve patient outcomes and the quality of care in the nation's fragmented healthcare (AACN, 2013). The CNL is the first professional nursing role in over 35 years that addresses the ardent call for innovative nursing solutions to today's complex healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013).

As a point-of-care leader, the CNL laterally integrates patient care in diverse healthcare delivery systems (AACN, 2013). The CNL is a generalist master's-degree prepared nurse who is responsible for the care coordination of a specific group of patients within a microsystem (AACN, 2007). A distinct skill of a CNL is the ability to focus on systems level thinking, while working at the point of care (AACN, 2007). CNLs infuse and advocate for evidence based practice to improve the quality of care. CNLs have been instrumental in the translation and implementation of evidence based practice in the areas of fall prevention, hospital acquired infections, patient education, and interdisciplinary rounds (Ott et al., 2009; Stanley et al., 2008; Wilson et al., 2012). CNLs also monitor and evaluate quality trends and patient outcomes (AACN, 2007).

The distinct function of nurses in the CNL role in a healthcare system makes it is essential that healthcare organizations appropriately monitor and assess CNL abilities to effectively fulfill the role. Clinical competencies are valuable tools used to identify personal qualities that relate to effective and successful job performance (McClelland, 1973). In 2007, the AACN established CNL curriculum and end of program competencies that were significant for CNL role success. In 2011, the Commission on Nurse Certification (CNC) led a national team to study the CNL role with the goal of

updating the CNL certification examine. The results of the literature search and feedback from subject experts led to an extensive list of CNL focused tasks, skills and knowledge needed for competent practice (CNC, 2011). As the nation's healthcare system continued to evolve, so has the CNL role (AACN, 2013). There was a need to reevaluate the CNL curriculum and practice competencies (AACN, 2013). In 2013, AACN convened a national expert panel and external validation panel of nursing leaders and practicing CNLs to identify new master's essentials for curricula and new entry-level CNL practice competencies. These new CNL competencies will serve to guide CNL education and practice nationwide. These competencies replaced the competencies in the White Paper on Education and Role of the Clinical Nurse Leader (AACN, 2007).

Problem Statement

Birth of the Clinical Nurse Leader

In response to the demands of a complex healthcare system fraught with fragmentation and a looming nursing shortage, AACN and nursing leaders created the CNL role as an innovative solution to the challenging healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013). There were several key healthcare quality findings and recommendations that inspired the development of the CNL role (AACN, 2013). In 1999, the Institute of Medicine (IOM) landmark report *To Err is Human: Building a Safer Health System* documented a dramatic number of patient deaths due to medical errors. A looming nationwide nursing shortage is expected to result in a 20% shortage in the number of nurse by 2020 (Buerhaus, Staiger, & Auerbach, 2000). In 2001, the IOM report *Crossing the Quality Chasm* documented the need for healthcare organizations and professional groups to advocate for healthcare that is safe, effective, patient-

centered, timely and efficient. In 2002, the report Health Care's Human Crisis: The American Nursing Shortage identified the need to rethink nursing education and healthcare environments with an emphasis on systems thinking and improving patient outcomes at the point of care (Kimball & O'Neill, 2002).

The number of CNLs and CNL education programs has grown since the role began in 2003. In the United States, in 2013, there were 3,620 certified CNLs. The number of CNLs across the nation was as follows: Northeast 548, South 1084, Midwest 973, West 1008, Alaska 4, Hawaii 1, Puerto Rico 2. Approximately 105 colleges and universities offer a CNL educational program (AACN, 2013).

The AACN recognized the importance of strategically developing a new type of nurses (2013). They discerned that simply increasing the number of nurses was not going to significantly improve and transform the complex landscape of the American healthcare system. Nurses in the CNL role were needed to resourcefully address the evolving global, technology based, interdisciplinary, and culturally diverse healthcare system (AACN, 2013).

Clinical Nurse Leader Role

The CNL is a generalist master's-degree prepared nurse who is responsible for the care coordination of a specific group of patients within a microsystem (AACN, 2007). A distinct skill of CNLs is the ability to focus on systems-level thinking, while working at the point of care. CNLs infuse and advocate for evidence-based practice within the microsystems to improve the quality of care. CNLs also monitor and evaluate patient and staff quality outcomes (AACN, 2007).

According to the AACN (2013), there are fundamental characteristics of CNL practice. CNLs provide clinical leadership for patient-care practices and delivery, including the design, coordination, and evaluation of care for individuals, families, groups, and populations. CNLs work collaboratively to identify, evaluate and improvement of point-of-care outcomes. CNLs anticipate risk and work with frontline nurses to design and implement evidence-based practice. CNLs serve as team leaders who collaborate with interdisciplinary and inter professional team members. Lastly, CNLs advocate for patients, families, and communities. Given these specific responsibilities, persons assuming the new role must be properly educated and evaluated on their ability to successfully fulfill the role in practice (AACN, 2013).

The CNL role is not a replacement for already established professional nursing roles (Thompson & Lulham, 2007). Rather the CNL role complements and collaborates with diverse nursing and interdisciplinary roles to improve healthcare delivery systems and patient outcomes. The CNL role is different from the clinical nurse specialist (CNS) nursing role (Thompson & Lulham, 2007).

Clinical Competencies

There are various definitions of the term competency (Miller, Flynn, & Umada, 1998). Competency is associated with having the knowledge, skills, behavior, and ability to perform required duties appropriately (Miller et al., 1998). Clinical competencies are valuable tools used to identify personal qualities that relate to effective and successful job performance (Levine & Johnson, 2014; McClelland, 1973). Competencies have been utilized in diverse professions and disciplines to assess the skills and capabilities of staff members to function in their jobs (McClelland, 1973).

In the 1990s, the nursing profession began utilizing competencies to evaluate nurses in clinical and education settings (Bradshaw, 1997). Nursing competencies have been used to assess knowledge, confidence, and ability to perform clinical roles (AACN, 2013). Clinical nursing practice competencies have been developed for diverse nursing roles (Cross et al., 2006; Kring, 2008). Competencies have also been developed to meet national quality and safety standards (Boylan & Westra, 1998).

National healthcare organizations began to implement competencies in their regulatory quality and safety initiatives (Boylan & Westra, 1998). In 1995, the Joint Commission initiated the Agenda for Change. This national quality initiative required healthcare organizations to identify and maintain all qualifications and performance competencies for staff positions (The Joint Commission, 1995). The Joint Commission standards of competency included new employee orientation to knowledge and skills needed for job performance, ongoing education and competency evaluation to maintain competency skills, and employee performance evaluation. As a result, all health care organizations that employ professional nurses and desire to meet national quality standards require their employees to complete clinical practice competency evaluations (The Joint Commission, 1995).

The 2013 CNL competencies are valuable tools to standardize and advance CNL education and practice nationwide (AACN, 2013). There is a clear need for healthcare organizations to develop practical evidence based CNL practice competencies to ensure successful and effective use of nurses serving in the CNL role (AACN, 2013).

Framework

The supporting framework incorporated in this doctoral project is Donna Wright's Competency Assessment Model. The model received approval to be used in this doctoral project as seen in Appendix A. This framework supports the creation of competencies that cultivate nursing staff engagement, accountability, transparency, and meaningful outcomes.

Donna Wright's Competency Assessment Model is useful because it focuses on a competency assessment process that is meaningful to staff while giving them tools to provide safe and effective patient care. The model also emphasizes outcomes that produce staff and leadership accountability. This model is valuable in the development and implementation of competencies in healthcare organizations (Wright, 2005).

There are three main elements to the Model as seen in Figure 1. These include (a) competencies collaboratively identified, (b) employee-centered verification, and (c) leader-created culture of success with a dual focus (Wright, 2005). The first element (competencies collaboratively identified) embraces the significance of engaging staff in the identification of meaningful and useful competencies in CNL role definition. The second element (employee-centered verification) involves employees being able to select from a selection of verification methods. The third element involves leaders creating a culture of success with a focus on supporting the organizational mission and positive employee behavior (Wright, 2005).

Donna Wright's Competency Assessment Model has been used extensively in diverse healthcare systems. The model also supports the doctoral project's identified goals.

Figure 1. The Donna Wright's Competency Assessment Model. Adapted from "The Ultimate Guide to Competency Assessment in Health Care," by D. Wright, 2005, p. xiii. Copyright 2005 by Donna Wright.

Project Goals

The main goal of my Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to development meaningful clinical nurse leader (CNL) practice competency forms for a healthcare organization as seen in Appendix B. During the inquiry and development process of the competency forms, the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) Model was created. Consequently, the second goal of my DNP project was to write two manuscripts for submission to the *Journal of Professional Nursing* as seen in Appendix C and Appendix D. These manuscripts describe the establishment of the CNL PIC Model as well as the CNL practice competency forms.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Clinical Nurse Leader Role

CNLs deliver clinical leadership across different healthcare settings (AACN, 2013). The CNL role is implemented in various healthcare settings serving diverse populations (AACN, 2013; Hinebaugh & Calamaro, 2011; Keiswetter & Brotemarkle, 2010; Seed, Torkelson, & Karshmer, 2009; S. Smith, Manfredi, Hagos, Drummond-Hutch, & Moore, 2006). CNLs are employed in numerous settings such as urban medical centers, rural community hospitals, acute inpatient units, outpatient clinics, and public health settings (AACN, 2013; Jukkala, Greenwood, Lander, & Hopkins, 2010; Shipman, Stanton, Hankins, & Odom-Bartel, 2013). CNLs work in diverse specialties ranging from pediatrics, geriatrics, intensive care, medical/surgical, public health, and mental health (AACN, 2013; Keiswetter & Brotemarkle, 2010; Seed et al., 2009; Shipman et al., 2013).

CNLs promote evidence based practice through point-of-care clinical practice as well as patient and staff education (AACN, 2013; Jukkala et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2012). CNLs cultivate the use of evidence-based practice by leading the identification and implementation of evidence based clinical interventions throughout the micro-system (Keiswetter & Brotemarkle, 2010; Seed et al., 2009; Wilson et al., 2012). CNLs serve as valuable clinical and educational resources for patients and staff (AACN, 2013; Hinebaugh & Calamaro, 2011; O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012).

CNLs are lateral integrators of care that lead effective care coordination within a micro-system (AACN, 2013; Harris, Tornabeni, & Walters, 2006). CNLs initiate and engage healthcare teams to ensure synchronized, safe and quality care is provided

(Jukkala et al., 2010; Sherman, Edwards, Giovengo, & Hilton, 2009). To improve care coordination, CNLs identify and promote evidence-based and systems theory strategies to solve clinical problems (AACN, 2013; Shipman et al., 2013). CNLs are skilled at connecting the gaps in the healthcare delivery system (Harris, Stanley, & Rosseter, 2011; O'Grady & VanGraafeildand, 2012). CNLs are trained to recognize subtle changes in patient conditions, communicate clinical findings to the interdisciplinary team members, collaborate with other disciplines, and educate staff at the bedside to safeguard that competent care is provided (Harris et al., 2006; Wilson et al., 2012).

CNLs collaborate with interdisciplinary team members to improve patient care (AACN, 2013; Bender, Connelly & Brown, 2013; Harris et al., 2011). CNLs inspire multidisciplinary strategies in the development, coordination, and evaluation of clinical interventions and treatment planning (AACN, 2013; Shipman et al., 2013). CNLs use effective group process and leadership skills to engage various staff members in cooperative and meaningful clinical practice (AACN, 2013; O'Gady & VanGraafeiland, 2012; Shipman et al., 2013).

CNLs cultivate seamless communication among patients, families, nurses, and treatment team members (AACN, 2013; Sherman, et al., 2009). Wilson and colleagues (2013) found that CNLs improved nurse communication patterns through the development and implementation of a standardized shift report tool. Through shared governance models, CNLs empower nurses to identify and voice their thoughts and concerns about their nursing practice in a safe and structured manner (S. Smith et al., 2006). CNLs facilitate synchronized communication among staff member through their essential role as a clinical resource and mentor (AACN, 2013; Harris et al., 2011). CNL

education curriculum emphasizes interdisciplinary collaboration (AACN, 2013). CNLs are educated on the importance of leading effective communication strategies and group process (AACN, 2013). Thus, CNLs are skilled at using interpersonal skills and established networks to promote collaboration and cohesion among staff and healthcare organizations (Wilson et al., 2013).

CNLs are valuable advocates for patients, families, and nurses (AACN, 2013; O'Brien & Harland, 2013). CNLs develop trusting relationships with patients and families that enable them to discover individualized needs and treatment preferences (Sherman et al., 2009). CNLs integrate evidence-based practice and patient-centered care interventions to support and individualize patient needs and preferences (AACN, 2013; O'Brien & Harland, 2013). CNLs also inspire a supportive work environment for new graduate nurses (Sherman et al., 2009). CNLs encourage and advocate for the comprehensive development of clinical skills and decision making of nurses especially, new nurses (Sherman et al., 2009).

The CNL role strategically supports frontline areas in the healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013; O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012). The distinct role the CNL plays in a healthcare system has been found to result in valuable contributions to healthcare organizations (Harris et al., 2006; Sherman et al., 2009; Wilson et al., 2012).

Clinical Nurse Leader Impact and Outcomes

In the brief time it has been in existence, the CNL role has been associated with improved patient outcomes among diverse populations and healthcare settings (Harris et al., 2006; Sherman et al., 2009; Wilson et al., 2012). CNLs are charged with integrating and maintaining quality in the clinical setting (AACN, 2013). Nurses in this role have

led and engaged in meaningful quality projects that have decreased falls, readmission rates, code blue events, pressure ulcers, ventilator-associated pneumonia, pain levels, and length of stays (Ott et al., 2009; D. Smith & Dabbs, 2007; Stanley et al., 2008; Wilson et al., 2012). Wilson and colleagues (2012) found that CNL-led unit-based initiatives increased patient compliance and education with influenza and pneumococcal vaccinations. Furthermore, having nurses in the CNL role is associated with increased patient satisfaction with admission process, nursing care, information updates, and care coordination (Bender, Connelly, Glaser, & Brown, 2012; Stanley et al., 2008).

CNLs lead and strengthen interdisciplinary teams and collaboration. Bender and colleagues (2012) reported that CNLs enhance interdisciplinary collaborative work environments. The implementation of the CNL role resulted in improved staff perceptions in physician and nurse communication, as well as daily physician and nurse team collaborations (Bender et al., 2012; Bender et al., 2013). In a qualitative study, Sherman and colleagues (2009) found that the CNL role enhances and supports the working relationship between physicians and nurses.

CNLs facilitated healthy work environments through evidence-based practice. CNLs are influential leaders who strategically promote principles of self-governance and self-scheduling to empower staff nurses (S. Smith et al., 2006). CNLs encourage other nurses to lead and participate in nursing led decision-making committees impacting clinical practice and patient outcomes (S. Smith et al., 2006). Sherman and colleagues (2009) reported that a CNL promoted a healthy work environment through the introduction of an evidence-based communication program and care-based practice model to staff nurses. The CNL and staff collaboration resulted in improved

interpersonal communication and bedside reporting techniques used by staff nurses (Sherman et al., 2009).

Nurses in the CNL role contribute to the development of organizational policies and quality initiatives (Lee & Calamaro, 2012; O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012). They have played an integral role in creating and facilitating evidence-based policies and protocols to improve patient outcomes and advance nursing practice (Coleman, 2013; Lee & Calamaro, 2012). Lee and Calamaro (2012) documented that CNLs were effective in creating and applying policies to improve clinical decisions determining nursing interventions for overweight and obese patients. Lastly, CNLs were reported to be skilled at organizing and supporting organizational quality initiatives with Magnet designations and the Joint Commission surveys (Coleman, 2013).

CNL advocacy efforts can impact and improve healthcare delivery systems (AACN, 2013; O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012). CNLs play an essential role in advocating for patients and families (O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012). CNL advocacy efforts have included supporting patient-centered requests, educating patients on new procedures, and supporting the development of new policies (O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012). S. Smith and colleagues (2006) found that the CNL role was associated with improved patient, nurse, and physician satisfaction.

Lastly, CNLs have influenced the financial and cost savings within healthcare organizations (Harris & Ott, 2008). CNLs have been associated with specific outcomes such as reduction in length of stay, infection rates, and nurse retention translating to significant cost savings (Hartranft, Garcia, & Adams, 2007; S. Smith et al., 2006; Stanley et al., 2008). CNLs have led collaborative quality initiatives in various

healthcare settings such as ambulatory surgery unit, inpatient surgical, gastrointestinal laboratory, and surgical intensive care unit that have resulted in dramatic organizational cost savings (Hix, McKeon, & Walters, 2009; S. Smith et al., 2006).

The CNL role focuses on providing collaborative, evidence-based, and integrated care. Persons assuming the CNL role must be properly educated and assessed on their ability to successfully fulfill the CNL role in the practice setting (AACN, 2013).

Clinical Nurse Leader Competency

The literature search resulted in a total of 24 articles on nursing competency. However, there were only three publications that were related to CNL practice competencies. In the literature, there were no research studies that focused on the development and utilization of CNL practice competency in the practice setting.

There is a paucity of research in the development and utilization of CNL practice competencies in the clinical practice setting. This doctoral project aims to contribute to the knowledge of how healthcare organizations can effectively develop and utilize CNL practice competencies throughout the organization.

The review of the literature supported a comprehensive analysis the CNL role, CNL practice impact/outcomes, and CNL competency. This literature review also provided support and guidance for this doctoral project's methodology.

METHODS

A review of the literature and internal communication sources (ICS) from a large United States health care system was synthesized. The collection of the evidence involved a literature search and a narrative review of the healthcare organization's ISC.

Ethics

As part of my Doctorate in Nursing Practice project, I met with members of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the large healthcare organization. After meeting with the IRB department supervisor, it was determined that I did not need to complete the IRB application because the data involved did not use sensitive identifiers. The organization's IRB department provided an email stating the exempt status as seen in Appendix E. This project was also granted exempt status from the IRB at California State University, Fullerton as seen in Appendix F.

Literature Search

A comprehensive search of literature using the CINAHL and PubMed databases was conducted for articles published between January 2003 through April 2014. There were two search phrases used: "clinical nurse leader" and "nurse competency." The search limiters were peer reviewed, English language, and publication dates 2003 to 2014. The CNL role was developed in 2003. Therefore, no significant CNL publication would be found before 2003.

The literature review search followed a systematic approach as seen in Figure 2. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, each database and search term generated a specific number of articles retrieved. As illustrated in Figure 2, the search using the terms *clinical nurse leader* resulted in 440 articles from both databases. The search using the terms *nurse*

competency yielded 142 articles from both databases. Articles were then excluded based on title and subject relevance and duplication. Articles that included historical perspectives, journalism, abstracts, and nonrelated commentaries were omitted from the literature review. Resulting were 25 articles for the final literature review. As illustrated in Figure 2, the articles were grouped into three categories (a) CNL role, (b) CNL impact and outcomes, and (c) CNL competency.

Table 1

Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Database Search

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used in literature review
Clinical AND nurse AND leader	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2003-2014	205	119	86	11
Nurse competency	Peer reviewed, English language	24	18	6	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 2

PubMed Database Search

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used in literature review
Clinical nurse leader	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2003-2014	235	149	86	14
Nurse competency	Peer reviewed, English language	242	124	18	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Figure 2. Literature search flow diagram. This figure illustrates the systematic method conducted for the literature search.

Internal Sources of Communication

The author examined the healthcare organization's ISCs related to the CNL role and practice competencies from January 2014 through January 2015. The ISCs included national CNL email group postings, SharePoint, and monthly CNL practice-focused seminars. SharePoint is a web-based site that has various resources such as CNL

articles, PowerPoint presentations, and contact information for CNLs within the healthcare system.

Analysis

The evidence was analyzed using a qualitative directed content analysis approach described by Hsieh and Shannon (2005). Directed content analysis can be used to identify key concepts and relationships between variables of interest and concepts.

There were several steps involved in the analysis. Each article and ISC was reviewed and evaluated for salient CNL concepts. Then, each was reexamined a second time and the written text was highlighted for significant CNL focused concepts. A written record was kept of the specific recurring CNL-focused concepts from both the literature and ISCs. The concepts were then examined for emerging similarities and connections. The most relevant and frequently mentioned concepts were then grouped into categories. There were 11 CNL practice and impact categories identified.

Publication

The two manuscripts will be submitted to the *Journal of Professional Nursing (JPN)*, a peer-reviewed journal that is the official journal of the American Association of Colleges of Nursing. The AACN was instrumental in the creation and implementation of the CNL role nationally. Readership of this journal includes professional nurses, clinical nurse leaders, educators, administrators, and nurse leaders. Author guidelines are available at <http://www.elsevier.com/journals/journal-of-professional-nursing/8755-7223/guide-for-authors>.

RESULTS

There were four key results of this doctoral project. The first was the establishment of CNL practice areas of impact categories. The second was the creation of the CNL PIC Model. The third was development of an organization-specific form for CNL practice competency. The fourth was the development of two manuscripts describing the establishment of the CNL PIC Model and CNL practice competency forms.

CNL Practice Competency Categories

As shown in Table 3, 11 categories were identified from the evidence related to CNL practice and areas of impact.

Table 3

Categories: CNL Areas of Practice and Impact

Category	Description
Care Coordination	Effective lateral management of care across disciplines and service lines
Interdisciplinary collaboration	Effective operation among disciplines
Quality patient care	Excellence in patient care
Financial	Cost savings
Satisfaction of patient and staff	Improved satisfaction
Staff retention	Reduced staff turnover
Quality/nurse sensitive indicators	Falls, infection rates, length of stay, readmissions
Team work	Staff working successfully together
Promotion of Evidence Based Practice	Facilitation of evidence based practice, protocols and policies
Communication	Improved hand offs and interdisciplinary interaction
Organizational influences	Organization's strategic plan, Magnet® designation

CNL Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) Model

The CNL PIC Model was created from a synthesis of the evidence. This model illustrates the influences that may impact the development and application of CNL practice competencies within an organization (see Figure 3). The model encompasses three contributory spheres to CNL clinical practice: (a) CNL Roles, (b) CNL Practice Competencies, and (c) CNL Areas of Impact and Organizational Influence. The CNL Roles sphere encompasses the identified roles and expected responsibilities of CNLs identified by the AACN. The CNL Practice Competencies sphere integrates content from the AACN's publication *Competencies and Curricular Expectations for Education and Practice* and the healthcare organization ISCs, as well as the author's experience as a practicing CNL. The CNL Areas of Impact and Organizational Influence sphere recognizes the diverse areas within an organization that a CNL can impact. While not incorporated into the model depiction, an assumption is that an organization's strategic priorities and initiatives are drivers of CNL practice.

The CNL PIC model demonstrates the interdependent relationships among the identified CNL role, practice competencies as well as organizational influence. The CNL roles identified by the AACN serve as a solid knowledge base for entry-level CNL practice competencies. However, as CNLs practice within an organization, CNL practice competencies should reflect the contextual and organizational influences in which the CNL practices. The CNL areas of impact are often identified and thus supported by organizational current and long-term goals. This synergetic relationship between organizational influences, areas of impact and CNL practice competencies are

The Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency (CNL PIC) Model

Tallakson, 2014

Figure 3. The Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model (CNL PIC). This figure illustrates the interdependent and dynamic relationship between CNL roles, CNL practice competencies, and CNL areas of impact and organizational influence. This model was developed as a part of the author's doctoral project.

essential in establishing, strengthening, and sustaining the CNL role within organizations.

CNL Competency Form

The CNL practice competency form includes nine sections that address the diverse knowledge and skills needed for meaning CNL practice competency in an organization. The last section entitled Micro-System and Organizational Priorities identify the distinct organizational needs that may influence and guide CNL practice.

This section promotes and supports organizational leaders, nurse managers, and CNLs to engage in a discussion of CNL practice and goals within the organization.

Manuscripts

The two manuscripts submitted to the *Journal of Professional Nursing*. The guidelines for authors from *JPN* can be found at <http://www.elsevier.com/journals/journal-of-professional-nursing/8755-7223/guide-for-authors>.

DISCUSSION

The findings from this doctoral project have valuable implications for CNL practice competencies in the areas of practice, education, and research. The CNL role is supported in the literature as seen in the table of evidence in Appendix G. The CNL PIC Model contributes to the understanding and integration of CNL clinical practice competencies within healthcare organizations. The development of meaningful CNL practice competency forms supports and promotes success in CNL practice.

Practice

Within CNL practice, a dynamic relationship exists between the defined CNL role, CNL practice competencies and the healthcare organization's strategic goals. The CNL role as defined by the AACN involves nurses with a versatile skill set who are able to improve the quality of patient care within clinical microsystems. Yet, meaningful CNL practice competencies can guide and shape the resourceful skill set of CNLs in micro-systems, mezzo-systems, and macro-systems of organizations. CNL practice competencies are embedded within organizations that have distinct culture, values, and initiatives. As illustrated in Figure 2, the relationship between practice competencies and areas of potential clinical impact and organizational influence is strongly connected. The two factors influence each other within an ever-changing healthcare system. For example, if a healthcare organization aims to reduce readmission rates for congestive heart failure patients, then a CNL in that setting should be knowledgeable and clinically competent and initiate strategies to make practice changes in this area. Organizations must take into account the complex and ever-changing clinical environment when establishing and implementing CNL practice competencies.

Both organizations and CNLs would benefit from CNL practice competencies that are infinitely adaptable and yet focused on organizational and clinical microsystem needs. Many CNLs have struggled with role identity and organizational integration (Klich-Heartt, 2010; Moore & Leahy, 2012; Stanton, Barnett Lammon, & Williams, 2011). Thus, developing CNL practice competencies that align with the values and priorities of a specific organization and microsystem would cultivate CNL practice and support the integration of the role throughout the organization. Lastly, CNL practice competencies should also consider the current knowledge and skill level of CNLs. The AACN's established CNL curriculum and competencies are appropriate for entry-level CNLs (AACN, 2013). However, for experienced CNLs, organizations must continue to ensure that clinical practice competencies reflect the skills of seasoned CNLs.

Education

It is essential that healthcare organizations employing CNLs provide educational support for CNLs who are transitioning into practice. CNL practice competencies that accurately reflect and incorporate both organizational and CNL evolving needs serve as an effective resource in the development of CNL residency programs. Organizations can also use CNL practice competencies to identify educational content and curricula needs of practicing CNLs. Little is known about factors that impact the implementation and effectiveness of CNL residency programs.

Research

There is a paucity of research on the development, utilization and impact of CNL clinical practice competencies in healthcare organizations. To date, no studies have examined how specific CNL practice competencies have impacted patient and

organizational outcomes. It is likely that the interplay of individual CNL characteristics (e.g., capacity) and organizational environment may influence the success of CNL transitions and effectiveness (Gilmartin, 2014); this is as yet untested. Organizational leadership and structure support can affect CNL confidence in performing various roles and skills (Gilmartin, 2014). Examinations are needed that describe emergent organizational priorities impact CNL practice competency, performance, effectiveness, and confidence in performing fundamental CNL competency skills.

Conclusions

The CNL role was created from a partnership between education and practice (AACN, 2013; Tornabeni, Stanhope, & Wiggins, 2006). Exemplifying an innovative nursing led response to today's complex, fragmented, and often-depersonalized healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013). CNL practice competencies need to echo the dynamic, innovative, and collaborative role that CNLs play within a healthcare organization. The CNL PIC Model reveals the interdependent relationship of the CNL role, practice competencies, and organizational influence on CNL practice. The CNL PIC Model also serves as a practical framework for healthcare organizations creating individualized CNL practice competencies. It is essential that organizations employing CNLs develop and implement meaningful practice competencies and CNL competency forms to successfully promote and guide CNL practice throughout the organization.

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APPENDIX A
FRAMEWORK APPROVAL EMAIL

Hi Melanie!

You can absolutely use Donna Wright's Competency Assessment Model in your project. We ask only that you cite your work (which of course you will :)) and then share your final results so we may save them for our history files.

I am CC'ing Donna because she loved to hear how her work is impacting the world.

If you need to use something from the book, a graphic or something, just let me know!

P.S. I am not sure if you know that we are about to release a new book called Competency Assessment Field Guide. It should be shipping on May 15 if not before. I can add you to our mailing list if you are not already subscribed.

Thanks!
Chris

Chris Bjork, PMP
Resources Director

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APPENDIX B
COMPETENCY FORMS

**Veterans Affairs Long Beach Healthcare System (VALBHS)
Clinical Nurse Leader (CNL) Practice Competency Assessment**

Employee Name

Date

Healthcare Group

Position Start Date

Unit

MARK ONE: Annual Review _____ Initial Assessment (new to Position) _____

INSTRUCTIONS:

Supervisor or educator will complete initial assessment during orientation (within 2 weeks of EOD) and annually. Note: Employees who have skills that are certified as “needs improvement” must develop an action plan for improvement and be reassessed by the supervisor or educator in a timely manner.

CNL Certification	
Date of Initial Certification:	Date of Recertification (If applicable):

Verification Method Codes	Certification Codes	Self Assessment Codes			
C = Classroom/Lecture DO = Direct Observation D = Demonstration DR = Document Review V = Verbalization S = Simulation	C = Competent N = Needs Improvement N/A = Not Applicable	C = Competent I = Independent Learning R = Request for formal Training N/A = Not Applicable			
CLINICIAN					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Demonstrate the ability to provide evidence based patient care accordance with established VHA and VALBHS policies and procedures.					
Develop therapeutic relationships with Veterans and family members.					
Subject	Self	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)

	Assessment				Supervisor)
Develop evidence based treatment plans.					
Facilitate modification of nursing interventions based on risk anticipation and other evidence to improve healthcare outcomes.					
Facilitate the implementation of evidence-based and innovative interventions and care strategies for diverse populations.					
Conduct a holistic assessment and comprehensive physical examination of individuals across the lifespan.					
Demonstrate ability to perform, teach, delegate, and supervise nursing procedures with safety and competence.					
Evaluate the effectiveness of health teaching and education.					
NURSING LEADERSHIP: ORGANIZATIONAL AND SYSTEMS LEADERSHIP					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Supervisor/ Educator)
Demonstrate knowledge of the Veterans Affairs and VALBHS healthcare system, vision, and mission.					
Understand VALBHS's healthcare delivery and payment model. Recognize principles/theories of business, economics, and value-based healthcare.					
Demonstrate working knowledge of participation in a leadership role of an interprofessional healthcare team.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Knowledgeable in strategies of how to participate in a shared leadership team to make recommendations for					

improvement at the micro-, meso- or macro-system level.					
Demonstrate working knowledge of how to evaluate the efficacy and utility of evidence-based delivery approaches and outcomes.					
QUALITY IMPROVEMENT AND SAFETY					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Utilize performance measures to assess and improve the delivery of evidence-based practices to promote outcomes with higher-value care.					
Demonstrate skill to develop a comprehensive microsystem assessment to provide the context for problem identification and action.					
Use evidence to design and direct system improvements that address trends in safety and quality					
Demonstrate the ability to implement quality improvement strategies based on current evidence, analytics, and risk anticipation.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Knowledge of how to promote a culture of continuous quality improvement within a system through use of safety tools, such as Failure Mode Effects Analysis (FMEA) and root cause analysis (RCA), to anticipate, intervene and decrease risk.					

Demonstrate knowledge of VA datasets, such as nurse sensitive indicators, National Data Nursing Quality Improvement (NDNQI) to assess individual and population risks and care outcomes.					
Understand how to use data sets such as Nurse sensitive Indicators, National Data Nursing Quality Improvement (NDNQI) to assess risk and outcomes.					
TRANSLATING AND INTEGRATING SCHOLARSHIP INTO PRACTICE					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Knowledgeable on how to facilitate practice change based on best available evidence that results in quality, safety and fiscally responsible outcomes.					
Understand and promote ethical decision-making frameworks for quality improvement.					
Demonstrate the process of retrieval, appraisal, and synthesis of to improve care outcomes.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Communicate to the interprofessional healthcare team, patients, and caregivers current quality and safety guidelines and nurse sensitive indicators, including the endorsement and validation processes.					
Knowledgeable on how to apply improvement science theory and methods in performance measurement and quality improvement processes.					
Knowledgeable on how to lead change initiatives to decrease or eliminate discrepancies between actual practices and					

identified standards of care.					
Knowledgeable on how to disseminate changes in practice and improvements in care outcomes to internal and external audiences.					
Knowledgeable on how to develop unit based and/or facility policies and procedures that promote evidence based practice.					
INFORMATICS AND HEALTHCARE TECHNOLOGIES					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Knowledgeable on how to use information technology, analytics, and evaluation methods to collect and assess appropriate and accurate data to generate evidence.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Knowledgeable on how to use information technology, analytics, and evaluation methods to examine patterns of behavior and outcomes.					
Knowledgeable on how to use information technology, analytics, and evaluation methods to identify gaps in evidence for practice.					
Knowledgeable on how to use technologies to coordinate and laterally integrate patient care.					
Participate in ongoing evaluation of the use of technology in patient care regarding cost-effectiveness and appropriateness					
Knowledgeable on how to use a technology and media to disseminate healthcare information.					

HEALTHPOLICY AND ADVOCACY					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Demonstrate knowledge on the interaction between regulatory requirements (The Joint Commission and Office of Inspector General) and quality, fiscal and value-based indicators.					
Demonstrate ability to articulate the value and contribution of the CNL role interprofessional staff and team.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Demonstrate the ability to advocate for policies that promote social change and improved care outcomes, and reduced costs.					
Demonstrate the ability to advocate for the integration of the CNL role in microsystem and the healthcare organization.					
INTERPROFESSIONAL COLLABORATION					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
Demonstrate the ability to create an understanding and appreciation among healthcare team members.					
Demonstrate the ability to advocate for the value and role of the CNL as a leader and member of interprofessional healthcare teams.					
Knowledgeable on how to facilitate collaborative, interprofessional approaches in the design, coordination, and evaluation of patient-centered care to improve patient care and outcomes.					
Able to facilitate the lateral integration of healthcare					

services across the continuum of care.					
Able to demonstrate leadership role in enhancing group dynamics and managing group conflicts.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Knowledgeable on how to facilitate team decision making through the use of decision tools and convergent and divergent group process skills, such as SWOT, Pareto, and brainstorming.					
CLINICAL PREVENTION AND POPULATION HEALTH					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Knowledgeable on the development and monitoring of patient treatment plans. Ensure that health promotion and disease prevention needs are addressed in the treatment plan.					
Able to design, delivery, and evaluation of clinical prevention and health promotion services that are Veteran centered and culturally appropriate.					
Knowledgeable on how to use epidemiological and environmental data from local, state, regional, and national sources to draw inferences regarding the health risks and status of populations, to promote and preserve health and healthy lifestyles.					
Use evidence in developing and implementing teaching and coaching strategies to promote and preserve health and healthy lifestyles in patient populations					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/Supervisor)
Knowledge on how to					

engage in partnership at the mico-, mezzo-, and macro system level to ensure effective coordination, delivery and evaluating of clinical prevention and health promotion interventions and services.					
MICROSYSTEM AND ORGANIZATIONAL PRIORTIES					
CNLs, Nurse Managers, and Organizational Leaders are encouraged to identify microsystem and organizational priorities that influence CNL competencies and practice.					
Subject	Self Assessment	Methods	Certification	Date	Initials (Instructor/ Supervisor)
1.					
2.					
3.					
4.					
5.					

Employee Signature

Date

Supervisor/Educator

Date

APPENDIX C**MANUSCRIPT 1 SUBMITTED TO *JOURNAL OF PROFESSIONAL NURSING***

Title Page

Title:

Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model: A Dynamic Response

Author, Highest Academic Degree Earned, Institutional:

Melanie Tallakson, MSN, MPH RN CNL
California State University, Fullerton

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Melanie Tallakson

Abstract

The purpose of this manuscript is to describe the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) model. The model was developed from a review of the literature, a healthcare organization's internal sources of communication, and the author's experiences as a practicing CNL. The CNL PIC model serves as a framework for healthcare organizations in the establishment and utilization of individualized CNL practice competencies. The CNL PIC Model embraces the dynamic and responsive relationship of the CNL role, CNL practice competencies, and organizational influences on CNL practice. In the model three factors contribute to CNL clinical practice: CNL roles, CNL practice competencies, CNL areas of impact and organizational influence.

Highlights (3-5 bullets, max 85 characters)

- Developed from a review of the literature, an organization's internal sources of communication, and the author's personal experiences as a practicing clinical nurse leader, the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) model embraces the dynamic relationship of the CNL role, CNL practice competencies, as well as organizational influences on CNL practice.

- CNL practice competencies may be shaped by organizational priorities and quality initiatives.
- The CNL PIC model serves as a practical framework for healthcare organizations to create and use meaningful CNL practice competencies.

Keywords

clinical nurse leader, clinical practice competency, CNL PIC Model

Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency (CNL PIC) Model: A Dynamic Response

Melanie Tallakson

Arrival of the Clinical Nurse Leader

The American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN) proposed the Clinical Nurse Leader (CNL) role in 2003 as a new nursing role intended to improve patient outcomes and the quality of care in the nation's fragmented healthcare (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, 2013). The CNL is the first professional nursing role in over 35 years that addresses the ardent call for innovative nursing solutions to today's complex healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013).

Clinical Nurse Leader Role

As a point-of-care leader, the CNL laterally integrates patient care in diverse healthcare delivery systems (AACN, 2013). The CNL is a generalist master's-degree prepared nurse who is responsible for care coordination of a specific group of patients within a clinical microsystem (AACN, 2007). A distinct skill of a CNL is the ability to focus on systems level thinking, while working at the point of care (AACN, 2007). CNLs infuse and advocate for evidence-based practice to improve the quality of patient care. CNLs have been instrumental in translation and implementation of evidence-based practice in the areas of fall prevention, hospital acquired infections, patient education, and interdisciplinary rounding (Ott et al., 2009; Stanton, et al.; 2008; Wilson et al., 2013). CNLs also monitor and evaluate quality trends and patient outcomes (AACN, 2007).

Clinical Practice Competencies

Competencies are tools used to identify personal qualities that relate to effective and successful job performance (McClelland, 1973). In the 1990s, nurse leaders began using competencies to guide evaluations of nurses in clinical and educational settings (Bradshaw, 1997). Since then, competencies have been used to assess knowledge, confidence, and ability of nurses to perform essential clinical skills and practices (AACN, 2013). Nursing clinical practice competencies exist for diverse nursing roles including nurse practitioners and clinical nurse specialists (Cross et al., 2014). Competencies have also been developed and implemented in healthcare organizations as they strive to meet national quality and safety standards (The Joint Commission, 1995).

In 2007, the AACN established the CNL curriculum and initial role competencies that were important for the success of entry-level CNLs. As the nation's delivery healthcare system evolved, so did the needs and functions of those in the CNL roles (AACN, 2013). In 2013, the AACN assembled a national expert and external validation panel of nurse leaders and practicing CNLs to identify new essentials of CNL curriculum and practice competencies. These new CNL competencies guide CNL education and practice for entry-level CNLs and replace the White Paper on Education and Role of the Clinical Nurse Leader competencies (AACN, 2007). As a result of the revised competencies, there is a need to examine the integration and utilization of relevant CNL practice competencies in the practice setting (AACN, 2013).

The purpose of this manuscript is to describe the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) model. The model was developed from a review of the literature, a healthcare organization's internal sources of communication and the author's

experiences as a practicing CNL. The CNL PIC model serves as a framework for healthcare organizations in the establishment and utilization of customized CNL practice competencies.

Methodology

A review of the literature and internal communication sources (ICS) from a large United States health care system was synthesized. The collection of the evidence involved a literature search and a narrative review of the healthcare organization's ISC.

Literature Search

A comprehensive search of current literature using the CINAHL and PubMed databases was conducted for articles published between the dates January 2003 to April 2014. There were two search phrases used in the literature search. The first was "clinical nurse leader." The second was "nurse competency." The search limiters were peer reviewed, English language, and publications from 2003 to 2014. The CNL role was developed in 2003. Therefore, no significant CNL publication would be found before 2003.

Literature Search Results

The literature search followed a systematic approach. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, each database and search term generated a specific number of articles retrieved. As illustrated in Figure 1, the search using the terms clinical nurse leader resulted in 440 articles from both databases. The search using the terms nurse competency yielded 142 articles from both databases. Articles were then excluded based on title relevance and duplication. Articles that included historical perspectives, journalism, abstracts, and nonrelated commentaries were omitted from the literature review. Resulting were a total

of 25 articles for the final literature review. The articles were grouped into three categories (1) CNL role (2) CNL impact and outcomes (3) CNL competency.

Figure 1. Literature search flow diagram. This figure illustrates the systematic method conducted for the literature search.

Table 1

CINAHL Database Search

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used in literature review
Clinical AND nurse AND leader	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2003-2014	205	119	86	11
Nurse competency	Peer Reviewed, English language	24	18	6	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 2

PubMed Database Search

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used in literature review
Clinical nurse leader	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2003-2014	235	149	86	14
Nurse competency	Peer Reviewed, English language	242	124	18	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Internal Sources of Communication

Following review by the healthcare organization's institutional review board and receipt of exempt status, the author examined the healthcare organization's ISCs related to the CNL role and practice competencies from January 2014 to January 2015. The ISCs included the healthcare system's national CNL email group postings, share point, and monthly CNL practice focused seminars.

Analysis

The evidence was analyzed using a qualitative directed content analysis approach described by Hsieh and Shannon (2008). Directed content analysis can be utilized to

identify key concepts and relationships between variables of interest and concepts (Hsieh & Shannon, 2008).

There were several steps involved in the analysis of the evidence. Each article and ISC was reviewed and evaluated for salient CNL concepts. The article and ISC was reexamined a second time and the written text was highlighted for significant CNL focused concepts. A written record was kept of the specific recurring CNL focused concepts from both the literature and ISC. The concepts were then examined for emerging similarities and connections. The most relevant and frequently mentioned concepts were then grouped into categories. There were 11 CNL practice and impact categories identified.

Results

CNL Practice Competency Categories

As shown in Table 3, categories were identified from the evidence related to CNL practice and impact. Each category describes a function served by CNLs or a potential outcome of CNL practice within a health care organization. For example, the category organizational influence may involve an organization's goal of obtaining Magnet® status. CNL practice can support and contribute to this long-term organizational goal.

CNL Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) Model

CNL PIC Model was created from the synthesis of the evidence. This model illustrates the influences that may impact the development and application of CNL practice competencies within an organization (see Figure 2). The model encompasses three contributory spheres to CNL clinical practice: (a) CNL Roles, (b) CNL Practice Competencies, and (c) CNL Areas of Impact and Organizational Influence. The CNL

Roles sphere encompasses the identified roles and expected responsibilities of CNLs identified by the AACN. The CNL Practice Competencies sphere integrates content from

Table 3

Categories: CNL Areas of Practice and Impact

Category	Description
Care Coordination	Effective lateral management of care across disciplines and service lines
Interdisciplinary Collaboration	Effective operation among disciplines
Quality Patient Care	Excellence in patient care
Financial	Cost savings
Satisfaction of Patient & Staff	Improved satisfaction
Staff retention	Reduced staff turnover
Quality/Nurse Sensitive Indicators	Falls, infection rates, length of stay, readmissions
Team work	Staff working successfully together
Promotion of Evidence Based Practice	Facilitation of evidence based practice, protocols and policies
Communication	Improved hand offs and interdisciplinary interaction
Organizational Influences	Organization's strategic plan, Magnet® designation

the AACNs publication *Competencies and Curricular Expectations for Education and Practice* and the healthcare organization ISCs, as well as the author's experience as a practicing CNL. The CNL Areas of Impact and Organizational Influence sphere recognizes the diverse areas within an organization that a CNL can impact. While not incorporated into the model depiction, an assumption is that an organization's strategic priorities and initiatives are drivers of CNL practice.

The CNL PIC model demonstrates the interdependent relationships among the identified CNL role, practice competencies as well as organizational influence. The CNL

roles identified by the AACN serve as a solid knowledge base for entry-level CNL practice competencies. However, over time, as a CNL practices within an organization, CNL practice competencies should reflect specific contextual and organizational influences and reflect the unique work setting in which the CNL practices. The CNL areas of impact are thus supported by the organization's current and long-term goals. This synergetic relationship between organizational influences, areas of impact and CNL practice competencies are essential in establishing, strengthening, and sustaining the CNL role within a healthcare organization.

Figure 2. The Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model (CNL PIC). This figure illustrates the interdependent and dynamic relationship between CNL roles, CNL practice competencies, and CNL areas of impact and organizational influence. This model was developed as a part of the author's doctoral project.

Discussion

The findings from this paper have valuable implications for CNL practice competencies in the areas of practice, education, and research. The CNL PIC Model contributes to the understanding and integration of CNL clinical practice competencies within the healthcare organization and reflects the maturation and maintenance of this role.

Practice

Within CNL practice, a dynamic relationship exists between the defined CNL role, CNL practice competencies and the healthcare organization's strategic goals. The CNL role as defined by the AACN involves nurses with a versatile skill set who are able to improve the quality of patient care within microsystems. Yet, meaningful CNL practice competencies can guide and shape the CNLs' resourceful skill sets within the microsystem, mesosystem, and macrosystem of an organization. CNL practice competencies are embedded within organizations that have distinct culture, values, and initiatives. As illustrated in Figure 2, the relationship between practice competencies and areas of potential clinical impact and organizational influence is strongly connected. The two factors influence each other within an ever-changing healthcare system. For example, if a healthcare organization aims to reduce readmission rates for congestive heart failure patients, then a CNL in that setting should be knowledgeable and clinically competent and initiate strategies to make practice changes in this area. Organizations must take into account the complex and ever-changing clinical environment when establishing and implementing CNL practice competencies.

Both organizations and CNLs would benefit from CNL practice competencies that are infinitely adaptable and yet focused on organizational and clinical microsystem needs. Many CNLs have struggled with role identity and organizational integration (Klich-Hearst, 2010; Moore & Leahy, 2012; Stanton, Barnett Lammon & Williams, 2011). Thus, developing CNL practice competencies that align with the values and priorities of a specific organization and microsystem would cultivate CNL practice and support the integration of the role throughout the organization. Lastly, CNL practice competencies should also consider the current knowledge and skill level of the CNL. The AACN's established CNL curriculum and competencies are appropriate for entry-level CNLs (AACN, 2013). However, for experienced CNLs, organizations must continue to ensure that clinical practice competencies reflect the skills of maturing and seasoned CNLs.

Education

It is essential that healthcare organizations employing CNLs provide educational support for CNLs who are transitioning into practice. CNL practice competencies that accurately reflect and incorporate both the organization and CNL evolving needs serve as an effective resource in the development of CNL residency programs. Organizations can also use CNL practice competencies to identify education and content curriculum needs of practicing CNLs. Little is known about factors that impact the implementation and effectiveness of CNL residency programs.

Research

There is a paucity of research on the development, utilization, and impact of CNL clinical practice competencies in healthcare organizations. To date, no studies have examined how CNL practice competencies have impacted the implementation of the

CNL role. Furthermore, no studies have examined how CNL practice competencies impact patient and organizational outcomes. It is likely that the interplay of individual CNL characteristics (e.g., capacity) and organizational environment may influence the success of CNL transitions and effectiveness (Gilmartin, 2014); this is as yet untested. Organizational leadership and structure support can affect CNL confidence in performing various roles and skills (Gilmartin, 2014). Beneficial future research could examine how emergent organizational priorities impact CNL practice competency, performance, effectiveness, and confidence in performing fundamental CNL competency skills.

Conclusions

The CNL role was created from a partnership between education and practice (AACN, 2013; Torabeni, Stanhope and Wiggins, 2006), exemplifying an innovative nursing-led response to a complex, fragmented, and often-depersonalized healthcare delivery system (AACN, 2013). CNL practice competencies need to echo the dynamic, innovative, and collaborative role that CNLs play within healthcare organizations. The CNL PIC Model reveals the interdependent relationship of the CNL role, practice competencies, and organizational influence on CNL practice. The CNL PIC Model also serves as a practical framework for healthcare organizations creating individualized CNL practice competencies. It is essential that organizations employing CNLs develop and implement meaningful practice competencies and CNL competency forms to successfully promote and guide CNL practice throughout the organization.

NOTE: The references used in the manuscript can be found in the Project Reference list on pages 25-28.

APPENDIX D**MANUSCRIPT 2 SUBMITTED TO *JOURNAL OF PROFESSIONAL NURSING***

Title Page

Title:

Creating Meaningful Clinical Nurse Leader Practice Competencies: Application of the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model

Author, Highest Academic Degree Earned, Institutional:

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Melanie Tallakson

Abstract

The Clinical Nurse Leader (CNL) role was generated from a collaborative partnership between nursing education and clinical practice. Developed in 2013 as a point-of-care leader, the CNL improves patient outcomes and promote quality care in the nation's fragmented healthcare system. The CNL role is a nursing led innovation developed in response to the current healthcare environment. Given the distinct role CNLs play within the healthcare team, evidence-based practice competencies are essential to ensure that organizations are successfully and strategically employing nurses in the CNL role. Practice competencies are used to evaluate nurses in clinical and educational settings. Thus, organizations that employ nurses in CNL roles would benefit from using CNL-focused practice competency forms to support and guide CNL practice. The purpose of this manuscript is to describe potential uses of the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) model and specific application of its use in creating CNL practice competency forms for a healthcare organization.

Highlights (3-5 bullets, max 85 characters)

- Healthcare organizations and nursing leaders can use the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact (CNL PIC) model to guide the development of meaningful CNL practice competencies.
- The CNL PIC model promotes transformational dialogue and strategic planning between organizational leaders, nurse leaders, and CNLs to support quality patient care and organization influences/goals.
- The CNL PIC model serves as a practical and dynamic framework for healthcare organizations to support, maintain, and evaluate CNL practice within an organization.

Keywords

clinical nurse leader, clinical practice competency, CNL PIC Model, organizational influences

Creating Meaningful Clinical Nurse Leader Practice Competencies: Using the Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model

Melanie Tallakson

Clinical Nurse Leader Role

CNLs are generalist master's-degree prepared nurses who are responsible for the care coordination of specific groups of patients within clinical microsystems (AACN, 2007). A distinct skill of CNLs is their ability to focus on systems level thinking, while working at the point of care. CNLs infuse and advocate for evidence-based practice within microsystems to improve the quality of care. They also monitor and evaluate patient and staff quality outcomes (AACN, 2007).

According to the AACN (2013), fundamental characteristics of CNL practice can be delineated. CNLs provide clinical leadership for patient-care practices and delivery, including the design, coordination, and evaluation of care for individuals, families, groups, and populations. CNLs work collaboratively to identify, evaluate and improvement of point-of-care outcomes. CNLs anticipate risk and work with frontline nurses to design and implement evidence-based practice. CNLs serve as team leaders who collaborate with interdisciplinary and inter professional team members. Lastly, CNLs advocate for patients, families, and communities. Given these specific responsibilities, persons assuming this new role must be properly educated and evaluated on their ability to successfully fulfill the role in practice (AACN, 2013).

The CNL role is not a replacement for already established professional nursing roles (Thompson & Lulham, 2007). Rather, the CNL role complements and collaborates with diverse nursing and interdisciplinary roles to improve healthcare delivery systems

and patient outcomes. With this distinct and versatile skill set, CNLs and organizations would benefit from organization-focused clinical practice competency forms.

Practice Competencies

There are various definitions of the term competency (Miller, Flynn, & Umada, 1998). Competency is associated with having the knowledge, skills, behavior, and ability to perform required duties appropriately (Miller et al., 1998). The term competency also includes the achievement of desired outcomes with the capability to extend nurse abilities beyond technical skills (del Bueno & Beay, 1995).

In the 1990s, the nursing profession began utilizing competencies to evaluate nurses in clinical and education settings (Bradshaw, 1997). Nursing competencies have been used to assess knowledge, confidence, and ability to perform clinical roles (AACN, 2013). Clinical nursing practice competencies have been developed for diverse nursing roles (Cross et al., 2006; Kring, 2008). Competencies have also been developed to meet national quality and safety standards (Boylan & Westra, 1998).

National healthcare organizations began to implement competencies in regulatory quality and safety initiatives (Boylan & Westra, 1998). In 1995, the Joint Commission initiated the Agenda for Change, a national quality initiative requiring healthcare organizations to identify and maintain all qualifications and performance competencies for staff positions (The Joint Commission, 1995). The Joint Commission standards of competency included new employee orientation to knowledge and skills needed for job performance, ongoing education and competency evaluation to maintain competency skills, and employee performance evaluation. As a result, organizations that employ

professional nurses and desire to meet national quality standards require their employees to complete clinical practice competency evaluations (The Joint Commission, 1995).

In 2007, the AACN established the CNL curriculum and initial role competencies that were important for the success of entry-level CNLs. As the nation's healthcare delivery system evolved, so did the needs and functions of those in CNL roles (AACN, 2013). In 2013, the AACN assembled a national expert and external validation panel of nurse leaders and practicing CNLs to identify new essentials of CNL curriculum and practice competencies. These new competencies guide CNL education and practice for entry-level CNLs and replace the White Paper on Education and Role of the Clinical Nurse Leader competencies (AACN, 2007).

CNL Role in the Healthcare Organization

The organization discussed in this manuscript is a part of a national healthcare system that employs a significant number of CNLs. There are currently 368 CNLs employed in diverse settings within the healthcare system. The healthcare system employs roughly 10% of the national AACN certified CNL population (AACN, 2013).

Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency (CNL PIC) Model

The CNL PIC model was created from a synthesis of the evidence (Tallakson 2014). This model illustrates the influences that may impact the development and application of CNL practice competencies within organizations. As seen in Figure 1, the model encompasses three factors that contribute to CNL clinical practice: Roles, Practice Competencies, and Areas of Impact and Organizational Influence. The CNL Roles factor encompasses the identified roles and expected responsibilities of CNLs identified by the AACN. The CNL Practice Competencies factor integrates content from the AACN's

publication *Competencies and Curricular Expectations for Education and Practice* and the healthcare organization ISCs, as well as the author's experience as a practicing CNL. The CNL practice competencies are grouped into related sections. The CNL Areas of Impact factors are areas identified from the evidence where the CNL role impacts healthcare systems. Lastly, the organizational influence factor recognizes the significant role the organization's leadership, goals, and strategic plans have on CNL practice. It is assumed that an organization's strategic priorities and initiatives drive CNL practice.

The CNL PIC model demonstrates interdependent relationships among the identified CNL role, practice competencies, as well as organizational influence. The CNL roles identified by the AACN serve as a solid knowledge base for entry-level CNL practice competencies. However, as CNLs practice within organizations, their practice competencies evolve and should reflect the contextual and organizational influences in their work settings. The CNL areas of impact can be identified and subsequently supported by organizational current and long-term goals. This synergetic relationship between organizational influences, areas of clinical impact, and CNL practice competencies are essential in establishing, strengthening, and sustaining the CNL role within organizations.

Application of the CNL PIC Model

The CNL PIC model serves as a framework to guide CNL practice competency in various academic and clinical capacities. Because healthcare organizations employing CNLs should provide educational support for CNLs who are transitioning into practice, CNL practice competencies must accurately reflect and incorporate both organizational and CNL evolving needs. These practice competencies may operate as a resource in the

The Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency (CNL PIC) Model

Tallakson, 2014

Figure 1. The Clinical Nurse Leader Practice and Impact Competency Model (CNL PIC). This figure illustrates the interdependent and dynamic relationship between CNL roles, CNL practice competencies, and CNL areas of impact and organizational influence. This model was developed as a part of the author's doctoral project.

development and implementation of CNL residency and transition to practice programs.

Organizations can also use these CNL practice competencies to identify educational content and curricular needs of practicing CNLs. CNL job orientations and continuing education programs may also benefit from the reflective and collaborative model. Thus, the CNL PIC model provides users with practical evidence-based direction for current CNL practice.

Using the CNL PIC Model to Develop CNL Practice Competency Forms

The CNL PIC model serves as a framework for creating practical and meaningful CNL practice competencies for organizations. The CNL PIC Model embraces the dynamic and responsive relationships among the CNL role, CNL practice competencies, and organizational influences on CNL practice. In the model, CNL roles, CNL practice competencies, and CNL areas of impact and organizational influence all contribute to depiction of nursing practice evolving within a dynamic organizational context.

Consideration of each factor provides an opportunity for organization leaders, nurse leaders, and CNLs to reflect and engage in collaborative conversations to support and guide CNL practice within organizations. As seen in Table 1, the author reflected on specific questions and engaged in discussions with organizational leaders, managers, and CNLs in the development of sample CNL evaluation forms. The interactive dialogue between organizational stakeholders provided support and direction to the author in integrating the evidence, distinct organizational factors, and goals in this process.

CNL Competency Forms

As envisioned, CNL practice competency forms incorporate nine distinct sections as seen in Table 2. These forms also include a section for the CNL and the evaluator to complete an assessment of each competency using a variety of verification methods. Additionally, the form contains a required section that allows stakeholders to identify and customized microsystem and organizational priorities. This section cultivates and supports the collaborative dialogue essential in implementing and sustaining CNL practice within the organization.

Table 1

Questions to Drive Development of CNL Competency Evaluation?

CNL PIC Model: Factors	Reflective Questions
1) CNL Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does each CNL role influence patient outcomes in the specific micro-system? Quality of care? Organizational mission and values? • How do you see each role being applied in the microsystem? Organization? • Which roles are most needed in the microsystem? Organization? • Which roles support the organization strategic plan and quality initiatives?
2) CNL Practice Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does each CNL practice competency influence patient outcomes in the micro-system? Quality of care? Organizational mission and values? • How do you see each practice competency being used and valuable in the microsystem? Organization? • Which practice competency skills are most needed in the microsystem? Organization? • Which practice competency group(s) best supports the organization strategic plan and quality initiatives?
3) CNL areas of Impact and Organizational Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do the CNL areas of Impact influence the CNL role and CNL practice competencies (skills, knowledge, outcomes) in the organization? • What are the current organizational goals and priorities that may impact CNL roles and practice competencies in the organization? • What resources are needed to support the CNL role and CNL practice to achieve these goals and priorities?

The sample CNL practice competency forms are designed to reflect current CNL and organizational practice. They are to be completed upon initial CNL employment and more importantly, when there is a change in CNL practice or organizational need. Thus, competency forms are responsive to the evolving needs of CNLs and organizational initiatives. There is no limit as to when and how the competency form should be used.

The competency form is a tool to support and guide CNLs and their employing organizations.

Table 2

CNL Competency Form Section Titles

Competency Sections	
1	Clinician
2	Nursing Leadership: Organizational and System
3	Leadership
4	Quality Improvement and Safety
5	Translating and Integrating Scholarship into Practice
6	Informatics and Healthcare Technologies
7	Healthcare Policy and Advocacy
8	Interprofessional Collaboration
9	Clinical Prevention and Population Health
10	Microsystem and Organizational Priorities

Discussion

The CNL PIC model provides a basis from which organizations can begin conversations to create meaningful and personalized CNL practice competencies. The evidence-based and reflective nature of the model guides and engages organizational stakeholders to discuss and develop practical guidance for CNL practice.

Practice Implications

The CNL PIC model guides nurses and organizational leaders to identify and appreciate the dynamic and shared influence of the roles, practice competencies, and areas of impact and organizational influence on CNL practice. The model reflects the vibrant and changing nature of the CNL role and takes into account clinical microsystem and organizational needs. Given this, CNL practice competency forms should echo this fluid and responsive nursing practice. Allen and colleagues (2008) found that the context

of the clinical and functional environment was one of the most critical components of a nursing competency evaluation. Furthermore, CNL competency evaluations may benefit from including scenarios reflecting the functional context of practice and organizational influences. For example, a microsystem that needs to improve staff communication during interdisciplinary rounds will benefit a CNL who is skilled and competent in interdisciplinary communication and collaboration. The CNL PIC model addresses the need for nursing competency models to be more responsive to the diverse work environments of nurses, rather than the linear sequence that nursing competencies have historically followed.

The CNL PIC model cultivates and promotes collaboration, engagement, and strategic goal setting between organizational leaders, managers, and CNLs. This model supports and endorses the implementation and sustainment of the CNL role within an organization. With many CNLs burdened with role identity and organizational integration (Klich-Hearst, 2010; Moore & Leahy, 2012), the CNL PIC model collaboratively connects and encourages organizational leaders and CNLs to work together to improve patient care. Coleman (2013) found that CNLs were skilled at organizing and supporting organizational quality initiatives with Magnet® designations and The Joint Commission surveys. CNLs can also support organizations working towards achieving the AACN's Pathway to Excellence designation (Tallakson, 2014). Thus, developing CNL practice competencies that align with organizational and microsystem values and initiatives should cultivate CNL practice and support the integration of this role throughout the organization.

Research Implications

The CNL PIC model offers nurse leaders and researchers opportunities for future study. Studies are needed to measure how the three contributory factors (CNL roles, practice competencies, areas of impact and organizational influence) affect CNL practice. There is also a need for studies to describe how using CNL practice competencies changes CNL self-confidence in practice as well as employer confidence in the CNL role. Lastly, researchers need to examine how the CNL PIC model influences and promotes the collaborative nature of the CNL role.

Conclusion

With the distinct role that CNLs play within the healthcare team, evidence-based practice competencies are essential to ensure that organizations are successfully and strategically employing the CNL role. Organizations hiring nurses in CNL role would benefit from using CNL-focused practice competency forms to support and guide CNL practice. The CNL PIC Model illustrates the interdependent relationship of the CNL role, practice competencies, and organizational influence on CNL practice. The CNL PIC Model thus serves as a real-world framework for organizations to collectively engage and create individualized and meaningful CNL practice competencies.

NOTE: The references used in the manuscript can be found in the Project Reference list on pages 25-28.

APPENDIX E**ORGANIZATION IRB EMAIL**

From: Rundgren, Elizabeth M

Sent: Monday, May 19, 2014 11:38 AM

To: Tallakson, Melanie B

Subject: RE: Inquiry: IRB Research for staff's DNP project

Hi Melanie,

It was nice to meet you on Friday. After discussing your study, it does not sound like it falls under the definition of Human Research.

“Research is a systematic investigation designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge (45 CFR 46.102 (d)). Human research involves obtaining either data through intervention or interactions with the individual or obtaining identifiable private information.”

Therefore, it will not require IRB approval. If you should have any further questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Elizabeth Rundgren

IRB Assistant

Long Beach VA Healthcare System

562-826-8000 Ext: 3301

POSITIVE QUOTE OF THE DAY:

“A reader lives a thousand lives before he dies. The man who never reads lives only one.” – George R. Martin

APPENDIX F**UNIVERSITY IRB EMAIL**

Del Rio, Natalie <ndelrio@exchange.fullerton.edu
6/24/14

From: Del Rio, Natalie
Sent: Tuesday, June 24, 2014 9:05 AM
To: 'melanie.tallakson@csu.fullerton.edu'
Cc: Rutledge, Dana
Subject: IRB Submission

Hi Melanie,

The application you submitted to our office has been reviewed and it was determined that no IRB approval is needed. Let me know if you have any questions. Thank you

Natalie Del Rio

Regulatory Compliance, MH-103

Institutional Review Board/IACUC

California State University Fullerton

Tel: [657-278-7640](tel:657-278-7640) / Fax: [657-278-7238](tel:657-278-7238)

Natalie Del Rio

APPENDIX G
TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Clinical Nurse Leader Role

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To examine the feasibility and acceptability of a CNL role to improve IC in a acute care setting. (Bender et al., 2012)	Descriptive non-experimental IV: CNL role implementation DV: acceptability and feasibility of CNL role IC: multi-disciplinary collaboration.	119 bed, US, urban academic medical center, 26 bed high acuity progressive care unit.	Survey: 6 item survey, Likert type scoring (1-5) assess perceptions of collaboration. Physician questionnaire and open Ended questions.	Physicians were supportive of the CNL role, identified improved IC and communication Increase CNL collaboration with multi-discipline staff. CNL role helps build team cohesion; synergy effect. CNL serve as role model for new employees to accept and embrace IC.	CNL role enhanced IC and team cohesion. Stakeholders input = CNL acceptability and feasibility. A facility wide directive or policy to improve support IC is needed.	Non-experimental design; convenience sample; non-validated tools.
To trace a patient care experience and examine the role and function of each interdisciplinary role. (Harris, Tornabeni, & Walters, 2006)	Qualitative; CNL role, tracer methodology, patient experience	Inpatient medical center	Chart review	CNL role play distinct functions in care plan, Role may influence decrease in LOS; improve patient satisfaction, cost savings, communication, staff turn over/retention	CNL role has specific functions in a patient's experience, Role can improve various areas in the healthcare delivery system.	Non-experimental
To examine CNL role in weight management in children. (Hinebaugh & Calamaro, 2011)	Article; CNL role, Obesity care, children and adults.	Pediatrics	N/A	CNL role may be effective in working with children and families with BMI > 95 th %; CNL are effective in providing education and creating guidelines; CNL role may promote healthy lifestyles in adolescents and children.	CNL role successful in coordinating complex needs of children with weight management issues and comorbidities. CNL can connect patients & families to community.	Non-experimental

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To examine the role of the CNL in rural hospital setting. (Jukkala, et al., 2010)	Article; CNL role; rural setting	Rural setting	N/A	The rural setting can benefit from the CNL role. Rural healthcare systems need fluid care coordination and evidence-based practice.	resources and programs. CNL roles can help improve quality and safety in the rural setting.	Non-experimental
To examine the CNL role in providing culturally competent care for HIV infected transgender persons. (Keiswetter & Brotemarkle, 2010)	Article; CNL role; HIV care, transgender persons.	Inpatient setting	N/A	CNLs can advocate for culturally competent care for transgender persons, CNL can provide customized education and care plans, CNLs can endure continuity of care, CNLs can influence organizational policies, and practices.	The CNL role can be effective in providing care for HIV infected transgender persons.	Non-experimental
To examine the role of the CNL in pediatric care. (O'Grady & VanGraafeiland, 2012)	Article; CNL role; pediatric nursing care	Pediatrics	N/A	CNL role can improve the quality of care in the pediatric population by functioning as effective team managers, educators, advocates, and clinician.	CNL role can be effective in improving care coordination and communication in pediatric populations.	Non-experimental
To examine the CNL role in improving the practice of mental health nurses. (Seed, Torkelson & Karshmer, 2009)	Article; CNL role; Mental health nursing	Mental health nursing	N/A	CNL role may help improve mental health nursing recruitment and retention; role improves quality in inpatient psychiatric unit; CNL in the mental health setting can improve collaboration among stakeholders, CNL role can improve outcomes and LOS.	The CNL role can help improve the nursing practice of mental health nursing.	Non-experimental

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To examine how the CNL role promoted a healthy work environment. (Sherman, Edwards, Giovengo, & Hilton, 2009).	Case Study; CNL role; healthy work environment.	St. Lucie Medical Center, Florida Med/surg unit & progressive care unit.	N/A	CNL role improved communication (peer & shift report) among staff; CNL role promoted continuity of care through consistent presence on the unit and face-time with patients and staff; CNL role strengthened relationships with patients and staff; CNL role improved staff retention and satisfaction; CNL also encouraged nurses to return to school.	The CNL role enhanced professional practice at St. Lucie. CNL role brings nursing leadership to the point of care.	Non-experimental
To examine the CNL role in the public health setting, specifically in the emergency preparedness. (Shipman, Staton, Hankins, & Odom-Bartel, 2013)	Case study; CNL role; public health setting.	Public Health department; Alabama.	N/A	CNL role effectively collaborated with several different disciplines and agencies; CNL role improved communication between team members, CNL role used system analyst skills, CNL role coordinated the management of information; CNL role can write policies and PI guidance; role promoted advocacy.	The CNL role offers organizations a nurse leader with valuable and multiple skill to improve outcomes. CNL role focuses on evidence based practice = improved policies and protocols.	Non-experimental
To discuss how the CNL role contributes to improve the quality of care in community hospital and tertiary care. (Wilson et al., 2013)	Case study; CNL role; outcomes.	637 bed; tertiary community hospital; Northeast US.	N/A	CNL role collaborative in nature; CNL role are the point of contact/leader for unit projects; CNL role resulted in successful CNL led evidence based interventions and outcomes = weekly interdisciplinary rounding, creation of standardized	The CNL role improved healthcare delivery systems at the bedside through evidence based approaches to improve outcomes.	Non-experimental

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
				protocols; CNL role resulted in organizational cost savings.		
To examine impact of CNL on 5 diverse microsystems in the Veterans Affairs (VA) Healthcare System (Stanton, et al., 2011)	Mix Methods, cross sectional, mailed survey.	U of Alabama CNL graduates, US.	Questionnaire: Mailed, 4-point Likert scale, 19 statements about the CNL role; open ended questions.	5 out of 8 CNLs use data to guide practice 63% indicated they had great involvement in effecting change in healthcare policy; 87% indicated that they function as a teacher/educator 62% function as pt educator.	A strong correlation with the 9 core components of the VA CNL role (White paper). CNL practice roles will differ depending on work place characteristics and location. CNL education preparation complements the CNL role implementation into practice.	Self report, small sample size.

Notes. CNL = clinical nurse leader; DV = dependent variable; IC = multidisciplinary collaboration; IV = Independent variable; LOS = length of stay; Med/surg = medical and surgical PCC = primary care coordinators; PI = performance improvement; Pt = patient; Pt Sat = patient satisfaction; sat = satisfaction; QoC = quality of care; Meas = measure; US = United States; VA = Veteran Affairs.

Clinical Nurse Leader Impact and Outcomes

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To describe how an acute unit redesigned their care delivery system to implement the CNL role. (Bender et al., 2011).	Case Study Kotter's Eight Change Phases Model.	119 bed US metropolitan medical teaching hospital 26 bed unit.	Press Ganey scores on nursing outcomes.	Increase in CNL and physician collaboration; Increase in staff nurse sat with CNL role; Increase in staff nurse support for pt care and care planning; Increase participation of nurses in research quality initiatives. Establishment of shared governance.	Improved pt and staff outcomes = success of CNL role & visibility with nursing executives CNL role can help organizational achieve Magnet status. CNL role may support career advancement for staff RNs who want to develop bedside careers.	Case study
Examine the impact of the CNL role integration into acute care delivery microsystem on QoC on Pt Sat. (Bender et al., 2012)	Quantitative, pre and post study IV: CNL role in a acute care unit DV: Pt Sat Scores.	119 bed urban US academic medical center; 26 bed high acuity progressive care unit.	Survey: 10 months before IV and 12 months after IV Other measures Pt Sat Scores.	Unit with CNL had improved Pt Sat on admission, nursing care, keeping pts informed.	CNL role can improve Pt Sat scores. CNL role may lead to sustained improvements overtime. CNL role did not affect Pt sat with physician care and discharge.	Sample size small, only 1 unit studied, only Pt Sat measured.
To examine the role of the CNL in improving IC in an acute care unit. (Bender, Connelly,	Descriptive; case study; CNL role; IC.	26 bed acute care unit,	Survey; Likert scale; RN and staff acceptance of CNL role. Written feedback	Physicians reported improved frequency and quality of communication, and IC with nurses; CNLs collaborated with multiple disciplines on quality	CNL effectively role model collaborative behavior. CNLs created a secure and collaborative	Non-experimental; convenience sampling.

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
& Brown, 2013)			from staff, CNL self evaluation .	improvement projects.	environment for newer nurses.	
To examine the outcomes of the CNL role resulting in a breast center's national accreditation.	Case study; CNL role; outcomes of organization quality project	Community hospital; northern California	N/A	The CNL conducted an effective organizational assessment; CNLs can advocate for organizational strategic and leadership goals (accreditations, Magnet designations)	CNLs are valuable and qualified to coordinate the development and evaluation of quality organizational initiatives.	Non-experimental
(Coleman, 2013)						
To examine the challenges and processes used by a for-profit hospital to create a sense of urgency, redesign care, and develop a business plan for the implementation of the CNL role.	Case Study Roger's Diffusion of Innovation Kotter's Change Theory	St. Lucie Medical Center in Florida, US, for-profit corporation; 194 beds 36 bed progressive care unit and 46 bed general med/surg unit	Core measures determined; collected pre and post	Nursing turnover Pre 6.13%, Post 3.2% Pt Sat: Pre 3.4, Post 3.46 Physician Sat Pre 2.96, Post 3.13 Core Meas-CHF Pre 91%, Post 96% Core Meas-Pneu Pre 80%, Post 85%	CNL role improved pt outcomes; role improved IC	Non-experimental
(Gabuat & Hilton, 2008)						
To examine the business case and outcomes for the CNL role.	Article; CNL role; business case; financial outcomes.	N/A	N/A	The author identifies steps to include in a business case for implementing the CNL role. Including cost benefits is important to strengthen business case.	A business case can be effectively made for the CNL role. CNLs can contribute significant financial cost saving to an organization.	Non-experimental
(Harris & Ott, 2008)						
To examine the outcomes of the CNL role in a 4	Case Study, CNL role, outcomes.	1,110 bed hospital system; Florida.	N/A	CNL role improved staff communication and work relationships; CNL role	CNL role influenced positive outcomes in quality	Non-experimental

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
hospital healthcare system in Florida. (Hartranft, Garcia, & Adams, 2007)				integrates teams and healthcare delivery systems; CNL mentors and inspired staff nurses to elevate their nursing practice; decrease falls and improved pt sat; 100% compliance with core measure.	and safety in the healthcare organization.	
To examine impact of CNLs in 5 diverse microsystems. (Hix, McKeon, & Walters, 2009)	Case study; CNL role; clinical, pt sat; financial outcomes.	Large federal healthcare system; ambulatory unit; surgical unit; GI lab; surgical intensive care unit; transitional care unit.	Surgery cancelation rates, missed opportunities, DVT prophylaxis, patient transfusions.	Significant improvement in missed opportunities and DVT prophylaxis; CNL role resulted in cost savings in ambulatory surgery unit an surgical unit.	CNL interventions improved unit outcomes. CNL role = cost savings.	Non-experimental; convenience sample.
To evaluate the implementation of a modified CNL role on a nursing unit. (Smith et al., 2006)	Quantitative, pre and post survey IV: Modified CNL role DV: Nurse job sat, nurse recruitment and retention, pt and physician sat, contract labor usage, and pt LOS.	Acute US urban hospital; 6 month pilot project 3 PCCs (modified CNL)	Survey Tools: CWEQ-II nurse empowerment. Physician satisfaction with nursing care: non-validated, 5-question Likert scale.	Overall quality benchmarks improved post survey: nurse job sat, nurse recruitment and retention, pt and physician sat, contract labor usage, and pt LOS.	CNL role improved benchmark outcomes and cost saving CNL role decreased reliance on agency nurses CNL role increased collaboration among nurses and physicians.	Sample size small; self report data, convenience sample.
To examine several case studies of CNL role implementation and outcomes.	Case Studies; CNL role; quality; outcomes.	Healthcare system; Florida.	Pt sat and staff survey.	CNL role resulted in several improved clinical outcomes: LOS, nurse retention, nurse	CNL role has led to significant quality and safety outcomes for the healthcare	Non-experimental

Purpose (Author, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
(Stanley et al., 2008)				satisfaction, care coordination, pt and family education, nursing involvement in their practice, pt loyalty with hospital.	organization.	

Notes. CHF = congestive heart failure; CNL = clinical nurse leader; CNO = chief nurse officer; DV = dependent variable; DVT = deep venous thromboembolism; GI lab = gastrointestinal laboratory; IC = multidisciplinary collaboration; IV = Independent variable; LOS = length of stay; PCC = primary care coordinators; pt = patient; med/surg = medical/surgical; Pneu = pneumonia; Pt = patient; Pt sat = patient satisfaction; sat = satisfaction; QoC = quality of care; Meas = measure.